

Investigating the challenges developers face in the process of complying with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD)

Dear participant,

Thank you for taking the time to answer our questionnaire.

This questionnaire is part of a survey on the challenges faced by organizations and developers in the process of complying with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD). It is aimed at professionals working in software development who are familiar with the practices and requirements of the LGPD.

It will take approximately 5 minutes to complete.

DECLARATION OF INFORMED CONSENT

By responding to this survey, you allow the researchers to obtain, use and disclose the anonymous information you provide as described below.

CONDITIONS AND STIPULATIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to answer the survey for research purposes and that the data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences and blog posts.
2. I understand that my participation in this research is completely voluntary and that refusal to participate will not result in any penalty or loss of benefits. If I wish, I can withdraw my participation at any time. I also understand that if I decide to participate, I can refuse to answer any questions that I do not feel comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researchers if I have any questions about the research. I understand that my consent will not benefit me directly. I am also aware that the author will keep the data collected in perpetuity and may use it for future academic work.
4. By consenting to participate, I give consent and freely acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as described above, and I give consent to the researchers to use my information to conduct research in the areas mentioned above.

If you have any problems or questions, please send an e-mail. Thank you for your cooperation.

* Ask a compulsory question

1. Do you agree to take part in this survey? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Skip to question 2

Participant profile

2. What is your age group? *

Mark only one oval.

Under 21

Between 21 and 25 years old

Between 26 and 30 years old

Between 31 and 35 years old

Between 36 and 40 years old

Between 41 and 45 years old

Between 46 and 50 years old

Between 51 and 55 years old

Between 56 and 60 years old

Over 60

3. Em qual Estado você mora? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

AC

AL

AP

AM

BA

CE

DF

ES

GO

MA

MT

MS

MG

PA

PB

PR

PE

PI

RJ

RN

RS

RO

RR

SC

SP

SE

TO

4. What is your level of education? *

Mark only one oval.

Undergraduate student

Graduate

Specialization

Master's degree

PhD

5. In which stage of software development do you work professionally? *

Mark only one oval.

Requirements elicitation

Data analysis

Systems modeling

Development/Programming Testing

Software maintenance and evolution

Other: _____

6. What is the nature of the organization you work for? *

Mark only one oval.

Private company

Federal Public Administration Agency

Research project/collaboration

State-owned companies (BB, CEF, SERPRO, DATAPREV, etc.)

Autonomous open source software project

7. How long have you been working in software development? *

Mark only one oval.

Less than 1 year

Between 1 and 3 years

Between 4 and 6 years

Between 7 and 9 years

Between 10 and 15years

Over 16 years

8. In relation to the issue of data privacy, you have*

Familiarity/knowledge of the General Data Protection Law

(LGPD). *Mark only one oval.*

Totally agree Agree

I neither agree nor disagree

I disagree

Strongly disagree

Skip to question 9

Challenges

9. Which of the challenges listed below do you face in your organization* to ensure compliance with privacy legislation?

Check all that apply.

- Lack of knowledge of the law: Lack of awareness about the importance of incorporating privacy measures into the software developed or a lack of theoretical knowledge about the legal requirements proposed in the law.
- Translating the law into a technical context: Difficulty in interpreting predominantly theoretical norms, without specific technical guidelines, which makes it complex to adapt legal requirements to the implementation of privacy measures in software.
- Budget constraints: Privacy is affected because the compliance process is expensive and time-consuming, and human and financial resources are limited.
- Lack of staff with expertise: Lack of a Data Protection Officer (DPO) with comprehensive theoretical knowledge.
- Organizational structure: Insufficient communication between privacy experts and software developers, resulting in inadequate implementation of privacy measures in applications.
- Ambiguity in the law: Requirements are not expressed in a simple and specific way, logos are subject to various interpretations.
- Lack of standardization of techniques/tools: Legislation does not provide specific guidelines on the technologies to be used, leaving organizations responsible for reaching a consensus on the definition and assessment of privacy.
- Lack of security/privacy policy: There is a lack of clear consent terms and security policies, such as notification procedures in the event of a data breach.
- Relationship with the user: Rights granted to data subjects by legislation, such as portability and deletion of information, hinder the organization's procedures.
- Prioritization of functional requirements: Factors such as tight deadlines and difficulties in implementing non-functional requirements, for example, are common reasons for not implementing non-functional requirements.
- Uncertainty of organizational processes: The developer does not know how some processes are carried out, such as backups and system audits, but only part of them.
- Difficulties with third-party services: Uncertainty about ensuring compliance with the law when using software development kits (SDKs) and third-party services.
- Shortage of guides/tools: Difficult to find adequate and specific design guidelines, and when they are found, the support is often insufficient for smaller companies.
- International data processing: Difficulty in ensuring compliance with multiple privacy laws for organizations handling global user data and which ones should be prioritized.
- Changes in the development stages: Constant changes in software, which generate increased technical complexity and require reformulations in privacy implementation techniques.
- Ethics vs. economics trade-off: Difficulty in finding a balance between respecting privacy and prioritizing corporate freedom.
- Identifying privacy requirements: Empirical knowledge about privacy but difficulty in eliciting privacy requirements that comply with legislation.

Impact on application usability: The addition of a privacy and data protection framework can slow down system performance or make the application unusable if the data processing power is not sufficient.

Other: _____

10. In your opinion, what are the biggest challenges in implementing the principles of the LGPD during software development?

11. In your opinion, what are the best techniques/practices that guarantee the privacy and data protection required by the LGPD?

12. Can you describe in detail how your team mitigates the challenges of complying with the LGPD?

13. If you have anything to add, please use this question.

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